

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE APPLICATION OF
GRAPHITE COMPOSITES TO AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS

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The increasing demand for fuel efficient automobiles in response to government regulation has led the automotive industry to seriously consider and explore the usage of graphite composites for a wide series of components.

In contrast to earlier fiberglass applications which have been primarily in non-structural areas much of the exploratory prototype work now underway in graphite is in major structural components where the high strength, stiffness, and outstanding fatigue resistance of graphite composites can be demonstrated. Design and prototype activities have included chassis members, bumpers, door intrusion beams, engine components, and suspension systems. Graphite composite components have been successfully designed, fabricated and tested with highly encouraging results. This paper will describe these activities in the areas of design, analysis and fabrication, together with test results and performance gains where applicable. The paper also discusses recent advances in the analysis of composites using the finite element method together with comparison of analytical predictions and test results. Finally the paper describes possible mass production techniques for graphite composites in the automotive industry together with economic studies and future required graphite forms.